

DUAL FIELD DUAL CORE SECURE CRYPTOPROCESSOR ON FPGA PLATFORM

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ABSTRACT

This paper is devoted to the design of dual core crypto processor for executing both Prime field and binary field instructions. The proposed design is specifically optimized for Field programmable gate array (FPGA) platform. Combination of two different field (prime field $GF(p)$ and Binary field $GF(2^m)$) instructions execution is analysed. The design is implemented in Spartan 3E and virtex5. Both the performance results are compared. The implementation result shows the execution of parallelism using dual field instructions

KEYWORDS

Crypto processor, FPGA, Prime field, Binary field.

1. INTRODUCTION

The term cryptography represents the encryption of data. For the secured data communication cryptography is essential one. With rapid increases in communication and network applications, cryptography has become a crucial issue to ensure the security of transmitted data. Cryptography is used now a days in a variety of different applications. Every application has its own design criteria and raises special requirements for hardware designs. While contactless powered devices have to meet low-power constraints, battery-powered devices need energy-aware implementations that consume as little energy as possible to increase the life-time of the battery. The most fundamental decision concerning future hardware designs is whether to use a binary-extension field or a prime field as basis of the used crypto processor.

A secure crypto processor is a dedicated microprocessor chip for carrying out cryptographic operation. For increasing the speed of execution this paper is designing the dual core crypto processor. At the same time for decreasing the power consumption this design is implemented in the FPGA.

This paper is concentrate to design a dual crypto processor used to execute both prime and binary field instructions.

2. RELATED WORK

Only a few papers companied binary and prime fields in hardware. Dual field arithmetic unit for $GF(p)$ and $GF(2^m)$ is designed by Johannes Wolkerstorfer[3]. This paper design the multiplication, squaring, addition, subtraction and inversion in both fields $GF(p)$ and $GF(2^m)$.

J. Goodman et al. presented in [13] a VLSI implementation of a dual-field arithmetic unit. Their so-called Domain-Specific Reconfigurable Cryptographic Processor (DSRCP) is not a mere multiplier for $GF(p)$ and $GF(2^m)$. It can calculate all operations required for elliptic curve cryptography including inversion and comparisons. These operations are executed on an extensive datapath which is controlled by a microcoded control unit. Main components of the datapath are a carry-propagate adder for operation in $GF(p)$ that takes three cycles for an addition and a reconfigurable datapath for operation in $GF(2^m)$. An additional comparator allows comparisons of integers or polynomials. The Montgomery algorithm is used for multiplication in $GF(p)$. Multiplication in $GF(2^m)$ obeys an iterative MSB-first scheme with interleaved modular reduction.

3. IMPLEMENTING PRIME FIELD AND BINARY FIELD IN FPGA.

In 1983, Blakley introduced an algorithm to perform Modular multiplication of two integers A and B modulo an integer M[4]. It is an iterative binary double-and-add algorithm. The main idea of the algorithm is that it keeps the intermediate result after each iteration below the modulus value, which it avoids final division. In this paper, the modulus M corresponds to p and we say it Fp multiplication. All arithmetic in Fp are performed in two's complement number system, which avoids input and output conversions like existing implementations [11], [12].

3.1. Fast Carry Chains for Fp –Primitives

The main difficulty of the Blakley algorithm is the computation of addition on large operands. The modified Blakley algorithm for large operands is shown in [5] and [6]. The use of carry save adder (CSA) helps to speed up the repeated additions on large operands. However these modified versions require at least one final addition on large carry chain. Some pre-computed values too are used by this technique which requires additional time and storage area.

This work exploits the features available in an FPGA device for efficient computation of Blakley algorithm on large operands. The specific features that are available in an FPGA device are efficiently utilized for developing arithmetic primitives in F_2^m fields in [7]. However, this paper looks after the same for Fp. The modern FPGA consists of 16 slices (or 32 LUTs) within a single row which is connected through an in-built fast carry chain (FCC). The FCC can perform addition on two 32-bit operands most efficiently compared to any other adder.Structures [8] . It is experimentally shown that on a Virtex-4 FPGA device the latency of a 32-bit addition using a fast carry chain takes only 5.8 ns, whereas the same using a carry look ahead structure takes 8.7 ns. Hence, fast carry chain is 1.5 times faster than carry look ahead structure for computing addition

of two 32-bit operands on an FPGA platform. In order to compute an addition of two operands longer than 32 bits, the FPGA will utilize more than one row which requires additional routing delay. For example, the addition (A+B) of two 64-bit operands (A, B) using a single 64-bit carry chain is slower than the same using three 32-bit FCC and a 2:1 multiplexer [8].

We develop an efficient 256-bit adder useful to F_{p256} -arithmetic using 32-bit fast carry chains. The repeated Karatsuba decomposition is applied on 256-bit operands. An operand is decomposed up to a depth of three for converting it into eight pieces of 32-bit operands. A 64-bit addition is performed by using three 32-bit fast carry chains with a carry select structure.

Let, $A = A_1 2^{32} + A_0$, $B = B_1 2^{32} + B_0$ and $C=A+B$, where A_i, B_i are 32-bit integers. We compute $A_0 + B_0$, $A_1 + B_1 + 0$, and $A_1 + B_1 + 1$ in parallel on three FCC. Then the carry out of the least significant addition ($A_0 + B_0$) is used to multiplex the results of the most significant additions. Thus the latency of a 64-bit adder is 1 FCC + 1 MUX, where MUX corresponds to a 2:1 multiplexer. Similarly, a 128-bit adder is developed by three 64-bit adders, and a 256-bit adder is developed by three 128-bit adders. Therefore, a 256-bit adder is developed from 32 bit adders.

Fig1. Architecture of F_p adder/subtractor/multiplier unit

Fig. 2. Internal Structure of a 256 bit adder

At every level of hierarchy it adds one additional MUX in the critical path. Thus the latency of a 256-bit adder is 1 FCC + 3 MUX delay, which is 9.9 ns on a Virtex-4 FPGA, whereas the latency of a 256-bit carry look ahead adder on the same platform is 16.7 ns, which is 1.7 times slower than the above technique. we develop a programmable F_p -primitive based on above 256-bit high-speed adder circuits. Prime field operations carry over are addition, subtraction, and multiplication. Fig. 1 depicts the overall resulting architecture of the proposed F_p - adder/subtractor/multiplier unit, where the internal dataflow of A256 blocks are shown in Fig. 2.

3.2. Architecture Description for prime field

Our first objective for designing such an integrated architecture is to reduce the overall hardware costs for computing three essential prime field operations in pairing computation. The architecture consists of several independent blocks which operate in parallel for accelerating the execution of respective operations. The whole architecture is subdivided into four macro-blocks(A1,A2,A3,A4) and seven micro-blocks (B1,B2,B3,B4,B5,B6,B7). The macro-blocks are used to compute the arithmetic operations, whereas, micro-blocks are primarily responsible for dataflow among the macro-blocks, the registers, and the I/O ports. The functionality of the individual blocks are described here.

- Macro-blocks A1,A2& A4 are 256-bit adders based on our proposed technique is shown in Fig1.
- Block A3 performs 2μ for an integer $\mu \in \mathbb{F}_p$. This is done by simply one bit left shift having only rewiring and no additional logic cells.
- Micro-block B1 consists of one 2:1 multiplexer that selects either $v1$ or $w1$ based on the most significant bits (or carry outs) of 2μ and $2\mu - p$ operations. Therefore, this block completes the $2\mu \bmod p$ operation.
- Block B2 selects either $s1$ or $s2$ as the input to the A3.
- Blocks B3,B4 and B5 help to compute F_p —addition and subtraction in A1 and A2. The control signal $c0$ holds zero for addition and one for subtraction. Thus, if $c0 = 1$ then block B5 selects $-s2$ else it selects $s2$. Similarly, if $c0 = 1$ then block B4 selects p else it selects $-p$. Block B3 completes the operation by selecting the correct result. In case of F_p - subtraction (i.e., $c0 = 1$), it selects either $v2$ or $w2$ based on the most significant bit (MSB) of only, whereas, for F_p -addition it does the same based on the MSB of both $v2$ and $w2$.
- Blocks B6 and B7 multiplex $t1$ (the output of $2\mu \bmod p$) and $t2$ (the output of $s1 \pm s2 \bmod p$) as the new value of $s1$ and $s2$ and registers, respectively.

3.3 Binary field execution unit for addition

Fig.3. Binary Field Addition Unit Block Diagram

The binary field addition is designed by using the XOR gate operation.

4. INSTRUCTIONS IMPLEMENTATION FOR PRIME FIELD AND BINARY FIELD

4.1. Instruction 1- Computation of F_p Multiplication

Proposed F_p -primitive follows the parallelism technique of Montgomery ladder [2] for computing Blakley multiplication algorithm in F_p [4].

Basic Blakley technique for computing $c=ab \bmod p$ with input parameters a and b is as follows

```

c ← 0
For i from 0 to k-1 do
    c ← 2c + a.bk-1-i
    c ← c mod p
return c.
    
```

The choice of this algorithm is due to its lower hardware cost and intrinsic adaptability to Montgomery ladder for parallelism. We rewrite it, in Algorithm 2 with parenthesized indices in superscript in order to emphasize the intrinsic dependency as well as parallelism of the multiplication procedure.

Algorithm 1: The interleaved multiplication based on Montgomery ladder.

Input: p , $a = \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} 2^i a_i$ and $b = \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} 2^i b_i$.

Output: $a.b \bmod p$

1. $s_1^{(n)} \leftarrow 0$; $s_2^{(n)} \leftarrow a$
2. **For** $i=n-1$ down to 0 **do**
3. **if** $b_i=1$ **then** $u^{(i)} \leftarrow s_2^{(i+1)}$; **else** $u^{(i)} \leftarrow s_1^{(i+1)}$;
4. $v_1^{(i)} \leftarrow 2v_1^{(i)}$
5. $v_2^{(i)} \leftarrow s_1^{(i+1)} + s_2^{(i+1)}$;
6. $\omega_1^{(i)} \leftarrow v_1^{(i)} + (p-1) + 1$;
7. $\omega_2^{(i)} \leftarrow v_2^{(i)} + (p-1) + 1$;
8. $c_1^{(i)} \leftarrow (v_1^{(2)})_n \mid (\omega_1^{(i)})_n$;
9. $c_2^{(i)} \leftarrow (v_2^{(2)})_n \mid (\omega_2^{(i)})_n$;
10. **if** $c_1^{(i)}=1$ **then** $t_1^{(i)} \leftarrow \omega_1^{(i)}$; **else** $t_1^{(i)} \leftarrow v_1^{(i)}$;
11. **if** $c_2^{(i)}=1$ **then** $t_2^{(i)} \leftarrow \omega_2^{(i)}$; **else** $t_2^{(i)} \leftarrow v_2^{(i)}$;

12. **if** $b_1^{(i)} = 1$ **then** $s_1^{(i)} \leftarrow t_1^{(i)}$; **else** $s_1^{(i)} \leftarrow t_1^{(i)}$;
 13. **if** $b_2^{(i)} = 1$ **then** $s_2^{(i)} \leftarrow t_2^{(i)}$; **else** $s_2^{(i)} \leftarrow t_2^{(i)}$;
 14. **end for**
 15. **return** $s_1^{(0)}$;

[In this algorithm, $x^{(i)}$ represents the value of x at i^{th} iteration, $(x)_n$ indicates the n^{th} bit of x , and $|$ indicates logical OR.]

The algorithm computes two intermediate results ($s_1^{(i)}$ and $s_2^{(i)}$) in each iteration. The data transfer inside the architecture (see Fig. 1) for computing $(a.b) \bmod p$ is as follows.

- The register s_1 and s_2 hold the iterative results $s_1^{(i)}$ and $s_2^{(i)}$ of Algorithm 2, which are initialized by zero and a , respectively, as specified in step 1.
- Iterative execution starts from $i = n - 1$ and goes down to zero as shown in step 2. This step is executed by a 8-bit counter, which belongs to the control part of the proposed design and it is not shown in Fig. 1.
- Block B_2 of Fig. 1 executes step 3. The modular doubling (as computed by executing the steps 4, 6, 8, and 10) and the modular addition (as computed by executing the steps 5, 7, 9, and 11) are performed in parallel. In Fig. 1, steps 4 and 6 are performed in blocks A_3 and A_4 , respectively, whereas, both the steps 8 and 10 are performed in block B_1 . Similarly, steps 5 and 7 are performed in blocks A_1 and A_2 , respectively, whereas, both the steps 9 and 11 are performed in block B_3 . During the execution of \mathbf{F}_p -multiplication Control signal c_0 remains zero.
- Finally, results of the current iteration are restored as specified in step 12 and step 13 in parallel B_6 and B_7 blocks. All steps from step 3 to step 13 of Algorithm 2 are performed within one clock by the proposed architecture. Therefore, to compute a multiplication in \mathbf{F}_{p256} the proposed design takes only 256 clock cycles.

4.2. Instruction 2- Computation of \mathbf{F}_p Addition

The proposed design executes Algorithm 2 for computing \mathbf{F}_p -addition. As described in step 1, the architecture initializes registers s_1 and s_2 by operands a and b , respectively. It executes steps 2 and 3 in blocks A_1 and A_2 . Based on the most significant bits of v_2 and ω_2 it produces the correct $s_1 + s_2$ result of $\bmod p$ in block B_3 as described in Step 3 and step 4. During the execution of \mathbf{F}_p -addition the control signal c_0 holds logic zero. The proposed architecture computes a \mathbf{F}_p -addition in one clock cycle.

Algorithm 2: The addition in prime field.

Input $p, a = \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} 2^i a_i$ and $b = \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} 2^i b_i$.

Output $a + b \bmod p$.

1. $s_1 \leftarrow a; s_2 \leftarrow a;$
2. $v_2 \leftarrow s_1 + s_2$
3. $\omega_2 \leftarrow v_1 + (p-1) + 1;$
4. $c_2 \leftarrow (v_2)_n | (\omega_2)_n;$
5. **If** $c_2 = 1$ **then** $t_2 \leftarrow \omega_2$; **else** $t_2 \leftarrow v_2$;
6. **Return** t_2 ;

4.3. Instruction 3- Computation of F_p Subtraction

Subtraction $a-b \text{ mod } p$.on the proposed design is performed by executing Algorithm 3.It is executed by the architecture mostly like Algorithm 2 with additional help by block B5 for $-S2$.

Algorithm 3: The subtraction in prime field.

Input $p, a = \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} 2^i a_i$ and $b = \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} 2^i b_i$.

Output $a-b \text{ mod } p$.

1. $s_1 \leftarrow a; s_2 \leftarrow a;$
2. $v_2 \leftarrow s_1 + (\neg s_2) + 1;$
3. $w_2 \leftarrow v_1 + p;$
4. $c_2 \leftarrow (v_2)_n;$
5. **if** $c_2 = 1$ **then** $t_2 \leftarrow w_2$; **else** $t_2 \leftarrow v_2$;
6. **Return** t_2 ;

4.4. Instruction 4- Computation of Binary addition

Addition of a and b in binary field is performed by the exclusive OR gate.
Result = $a \text{ XOR } b$.

5. EXECUTION OF PARALLEL INSTRUCTIONS

The Fig4 shows the dual core structure execution unit block diagram. The mechanism and regularity of data access for computing all instructions are fairly simple. The distribution of access to the registers and resolution of access conflicts are handled efficiently at the runtime by a dedicated hardware block called data access unit which communicates among the CAUs and the registers.. The DAU takes care of granting accesses. Therefore, a simple multiplexing protocol is used between CAUs and registers, which is able to confirm a request within the same cycle in order not to cause any delay cycles when trying to access data in parallel. The data accesses and instruction sequences are hard coded into the *sequence control* of the architecture which avoids the additional software development costs. The dependencies of the instructions are predefined and thus the access conflicts are known. The priority of the data processing and the respective execution is rearranged accordingly which achieves maximum utilization of CAUs.

Fig.4. Dual Core Structure Block Diagram

Fig.5. I/O Representation Diagram

The data access unit or DAU acts as a mediator while transferring data between CAUs and memory elements. Due to the demand of parallel access, the proposed crypto processor stores all intermediate results in its active registers. Each of the register consists of data-in, data-out, and enables lines. It gets updated by data-in lines when the respective enable signal is invoked. The crossbar switch (*results*) redirects the outputs of each operation to registers. Similarly, the *operands* are redirected from registers to the input ports of the CAUs. The respective select signals are generated prior to the above two redirection procedures by the sequence control unit. The *access control* block synchronizes the select lines of the multiplexers for operands and results. It also synchronizes the enable signals of registers for restoring the intermediate results. The *micro instruction sequence generator* finds the current operation type and generates the respective micro instructions which are nothing but the control signals. The respective values of control signals, which on the other hand, represents the scheduling of different operations on CAU.

Fig.6. Prime Field Addition and Binary Field Addition parallel execution waveform

6. IMPLEMENTATION RESULTS

The whole design has been done in verilog on Xilinx ISE design suit using a Spartran 3E, and Virtex5. Performance are compared with both the architecture. The design is verified for the following combination of instruction execution in parallel.

- 1) Prime field multiplication and Binary field addition .
- 2) Prime field addition and Binary field addition.
- 3) Prime field subtraction and binary field addition .

Example execution for Prime field addition and binary field addition waveform is shown in the figure6. This design occupy only 20% of area in spartran 3E and 25.6% area in Virtex5.

TABLE 1 Comparison of Implementation in Spartan3AN&Virtex5

Sl.no	Parameter	Spartran 3E	Virtex5
1.	Area	20%	25.6%
2.	Delay	30.83ns	14.94ns
3.	Max.frequency	32.43Mhz	66.87Mhz

7. CONCLUSION

The dual core structure executes the parallelism with both fields of instructions. This architecture is a sample design of crypto processor for executing prime field and binary field operations. Its design is a low power architecture that can be realized on moderate silicon area. This is the basic design of dual field implementation in dual core architecture. This design can be further developed for more number of Prime and binary field instructions. This type of development of the design can get a secured dual field crypto processor unit. This work can also be further developed for the superscalar architecture, which will increase the speed of execution.

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